

Genetic markers as a basis for the excellence of carcass quality traits in the Latvian dark-headed sheep breed.

Version 1

Description

1. Scientific Excellence

1.1. Background, hypothesis, aim.

The project aims to develop a panel of genetic markers associated with carcass quality characteristics in Latvian Dark-Head (LT; Latvijas tumšgalve) sheep, contributing to sustainable rural development and the conservation of natural resources. The project involves selecting lambs for feeding trials, grouping animals by carcass-trait quality, and identifying genetic markers for these traits using the OvineSNP50 chip sequencing methodology. Predictive modelling and biostatistical methods will validate the markers. Throughout the project, young researchers will develop new skills, with results published in scientific journals and presented at conferences. The UL will register the acquired scientific knowledge to safeguard intellectual property rights. Additionally, a unique biological sample collection and data platform will be established to support future research. The current project will help establish a new direction in livestock genetic research at UL, expand collaboration, and attract new partners from the Baltic States. This will promote comprehensive research in sheep genetic selection and support the integration of genetic technologies into practical sheep breeding programs in Latvia.

1.1. Background, hypothesis, aim.

This proposal supports the need for sustainable use of native animal genetic resources in sheep farming. By conducting comprehensive research to enhance understanding of the

genetic factors influencing animal-to-animal variations on favourable carcass composition traits, we aim to develop a cost-effective and rapid tool for genetic selection that can be used to analyze live lambs. This initiative aims to enhance marker-assisted selection (MAS) in sheep breeding, supporting sustainable livestock practices and conserving biodiversity. The project supports a knowledge-intensive bioeconomy by making local sheep breeds more productive and of higher quality. This is in line with Latvia's Smart Specialisation Strategy (RIS3).

1. Livestock production involves the use of natural resources such as water and feed and is associated with environmental emissions such as greenhouse gases and manure.

By 2050, agricultural productivity needs to go up by 70% in order to feed a growing population [1]. We are at a critical juncture where food systems must balance the need for sufficient, healthy, and affordable food with the need to preserve ecosystems essential to life [1]. Therefore, the use of natural resources for livestock production is a significant source of environmental stress. To solve this problem, new technologies are needed to increase production while ensuring environmental sustainability. The goal is to produce food more economically and more efficiently from an environmental perspective than current practices.

Latvia and the other Baltic countries have a long history of raising sheep, which is an important part of their farming industry. However, unlike many other European countries that use genetic technologies to assess breeding values, sheep breeding programmes in this region have traditionally relied on phenotypic data to select production traits. This is primarily due to the lack of performance-specific genetic markers for local sheep breeds, including the native LT sheep. However, breeders and sheepfarmers in Latvia recognise the benefits of genetic selection. They are increasingly open to implementing these technologies into practical breeding programs as they meet their goals of increasing productivity and efficiency (<https://www.laaa.lv>).

In addition to management methods that optimise productivity, it is important to select more genetically efficient sheep. Efficient animals, that require fewer natural resources are more environmentally friendly and economically viable [2]. Thus, there is a need to develop innovative approaches to optimise the use of existing genetic variation both within and between animal populations.

Marker-assisted selection (MAS) is a valuable tool for identifying desirable traits, such as carcass composition, by leveraging the relationship between DNA regions and quantitative trait loci (QTL) within breeds [3]. Although the SheepQTLdb (December 2023) contains limited QTL data for sheep, analysing single-nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) in local breeds shows promise for selective breeding [4]. The period from weaning to six months is critical for lamb growth, offering an opportunity to identify animals for breeding or meat production [5].

MAS can be used to select crossbred offspring with optimal genetic profiles and estimated breeding values (EBVs) or to predict the productive potential of lambs already born [6,7].

Genome-wide association studies (GWAS) have pinpointed quantitative trait loci (QTL) for carcass composition, encompassing bone density, across various chromosomes in Coopworth, Scottish Blackface, British Texel, Charollais, and Suffolk breeds. Therefore, genetic variants within specific QTL regions associated with productive sheep traits can be used as genetic markers for MAS in sheep breeding. Currently, two commercial DNA tests (LoinMax and MyoMax) target genetic variants in the Carwell and myostatin genes for this purpose [8,9].

The current project involves conducting a sequencing study of the sheep genome of sheep breeds raised in Latvia using the OvineSNP50 chip from Illumina, which covers 54,977 single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs). This will provide detailed genetic data for in-depth analysis of the genetic background of these breeds. Although carcass composition traits are not commonly included in sheep breeding programs due to the complexity and cost of measurement, their importance for profitability is growing. Genomic approaches offer significant advantages, including reduced reliance on costly phenotyping, the ability to select breeding stock at an early age via DNA sampling, and faster genetic gains [10].

2. Animal genetic resources are crucial to global biodiversity, but their variation is increasingly at risk due to the intensification of animal production.

Agricultural development trends are leading to increased genetic uniformity in livestock, with endangered breeds being lost and inbreeding rising in commercial populations. Much genetic diversity is being lost through breed replacement and crossbreeding [11]. Local sheep breeds in the Baltic region possess unique adaptive traits, such as disease resistance, climatic tolerance, and efficient use of low-quality feed [12,13]. However, there is limited scientific, economic, and genetic evaluation of these breeds in different

environments. In the future, their genetic diversity may prove essential due to changing livestock production conditions.

Therefore, the primary focus of this study is the native Latvian Dark-Head (LT) sheep breed, which constitutes about 23% of Latvia's total sheep population and 70% of purebred sheep, making it the only locally bred sheep breed in the country. Developed between 1927 and 1937 through crossbreeding Oxford Down and Shropshire sheep with local coarse-wooled sheep, the LT breed is known for its good productivity, lamb survival, and milk production. It exhibits traits such as fast growth and a long, vast body, which correlates positively with back muscle development.

LT sheep meat has been found to have a favourable amino acid profile and taste, though further improvements in carcass quality and muscle and fat layers are needed [14]. Previous studies (Project of the Ministry of Agriculture of Latvia, 2013-2018) on Latvian meat breeds showed that Suffolk lambs had the highest growth rate (over 450 g/day), like Charolais and Ile-de-France breeds, reaching 45-50 kg live weight by 4-5 months.

Our study aims to identify a panel of genetic markers linked to productive carcass characteristics in other meat sheep breeds in Latvia, such as Ile de France, Charolais, Texel, Suffolk, Dorper, and Oxford Down. This panel will then be introduced into the Latvian Dark-Head breed through marker-assisted selection (MAS), providing a novel approach to improving productive traits without the need for crossbreeding with outside genetic material.

Currently, no genetic parameters for performance and carcass composition quality traits are available for LT sheep breeds as well as for other native breeds in the Baltic region. The physiological determinants of quality of carcass composition traits or putative biomarkers used to analyze animal-to-animal variation in live lambs could be used as a cost-effective and rapid tool for genetic selection or management decisions.

Originality and innovative aspects of the research: The research aims to develop a practical methodology for predicting carcass quality traits using genetic markers obtained from the blood of live lambs.

In addition, the project is expected to enhance sustainability and efficiency in sheep farming across the Baltic region, as the goal of current study is also to increase cooperation between the Baltic countries and attract new partners to promote

comprehensive research into sheep farming practices in the region. By working collaboratively and sharing our findings, we can advance sheep breeding and promote the conservation of local sheep breeds.

The proposed research is classified as industrial research. This research focuses on developing new genetic markers to improve sheep farming efficiency, integrating scientific innovation with practical applications for sustainable livestock management and breeding programmes.

The research content incorporates a gender dimension. The project does not directly involve human subjects; however, its outcomes may indirectly affect the livelihoods of sheep farmers, especially women who are frequently engaged in sheep husbandry in Latvia. To promote equitable benefits, the team will effectively communicate research findings to all stakeholders, including women farmers.

The action will incorporate interdisciplinary aspects. To achieve the project goal, expertise in molecular biology, genetics, agriculture, and biotechnology will be combined with access to lamb samples, including blood and carcass quality data from feeding trials. We can use animals with predictable performance related to the main economic pathways (carcass composition traits) for further marker-assisted selection. In this way, synergies between the two topics will be ensured; a pilot study (LZP No. Izp-2021/1-0489, (2022-2024)) successfully implemented by UL and the current postdoctoral proposal. This continuation of research is essential due to previous valuable insights into genetic markers linked to meat productivity. The new project aims to further livestock genetic research at LU and address gaps in sheep genetics in Latvia.

Specific objectives of the project to achieve the aim will be as follows:

Objective 1. Characterise carcass composition parameters for meat quality in lambs after feeding trial I; assess the post-fat cohort with the highest, average, and lowest characteristics.

Objective 2. Scan the genetic background of Latvian sheep breeds' DNA.

Objective 3. Analyse associations between carcass characteristics and genetic background, developing a genetic marker panel for carcass composition traits.

Objective 4. Validate the genetic marker panel using predictive modelling in a secondary animal collection after the second-year feeding trial.

Objective 5. Create a data platform to provide access to sheep genetics and carcass composition data.

Funder

Latvian Council of Science | | LCS

Grant

Genetic markers as a basis for the excellence of carcass quality traits in the Latvian dark-headed sheep breed. (PosDoc projekta 1.1.1.9/LZP/1/24/027)

Researchers

Elina Leonova (0000-0001-6572-4518), Ilva Trapina (0000-0002-8345-8708), Natalia Paramonova (0000-0001-6375-3331)

Organizations

University of Latvia

1. Main Info

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2. Funding

Funding organizations: Latvian Council of Science | | LCS

Grants: Genetic markers as a basis for the excellence of carcass quality traits in the Latvian dark-headed sheep breed. (PosDoc projekta 1.1.1.9/LZP/1/24/027)

Project:

3. License

License: CC-BY-4.0

Access Rights: Public

Publication Date:

4. Templates

Descriptions

001_Database of identification and fattening indicators intensively fattened lambs (Group or feed trial 0) of sheep breeds raised in Latvia, created before the project.

Project of The Latvian Council of Science (LCS) - LZP-2021/1-0489 project: "Development of an innovative approach to identify biological determinants involved in the between-animal variation in feed efficiency in sheep farming."

LZP-2021/1-0489 project data on lamb samples of the year 2022, or A22 group, which consists of 76 intensively fattened lambs from six breeds and nine samples from the LT breed, which were raised in the meadow and are semi-sibi lambs within the scope of the study.

Based on the requirements of the breeding programme of the breeds, every year, the offspring of the sire ram, certified for breeding activity, are selected and analysed to estimate the sire rams. All lambs were born as twins, triplets, or quadruplets from different ewes, and health status was assessed before inclusion in the study so that there were at least two lambs per sire ram from the breed. This study was carried out in cooperation with the Latvian Sheep Breeders' Association at the ram breeding control station.

The database contains data on ultrasonography measurements of lambs at the beginning and end of the fattening period, as well as intensive fattening data—both real and calculated on the 90th and 150th days, including the amount of feed used and slaughter data. Ultrasonography data were used to calculate muscle and/or fat depth changes at the 13th rib during the fattening period.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The phenotypic indicators of intensively fattened lambs are collected in a database so that association analysis can then be performed in relation to genetic or DNA single nucleotide polymorphism genotyping results.

By collecting intensive fattening phenotypic data, it is also possible to perform an analysis of lambs fattened in a particular year and compare their data with other years.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

- Aggregate data
- Observation data
- Process produced data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

XML

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

100

KB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

Yes

1.1.7 If Yes, please indicate what data set are you re-using?

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/>

id: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8143154>, Type: null

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

The resulting database and its processing results could be useful for sheep farmers, who could evaluate the results of intensive fattening over time.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

Yes

Comment:

The databases will be fully available after contacting the authors, as the data will contain animal identification numbers and the database will contain information intended for publication and the preparation of know-how.

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

DataverseLV

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

R, Excel, notepad

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

When using data, a reference to the database, the project in which the data was obtained, or the authors must be provided.

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.4 How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

There is no time limit for data reuse, as data is information about a specific time period that can be used in comparative analysis.

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Data management involves entering measurement data into tables, calculating derived data, describing data sets, evaluating data quality, and ensuring data access.

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

Data will be deposited in repository and kept up to date

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Firewall
- Passwords
- Physical access control

The database will be created using security measures that will provide for data access control, as the data will be stored on a data medium that will only be accessible to specific persons. The data medium will have a password set for both the overall system and the specific database, as well as protections to prevent access from the Internet.

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

002_Database of previously significant 57 SNP genotypes of DNA samples intensively fattened lambs (Group or feed trial 0) of sheep breeds raised in Latvia, created before the project.

The LZP-2021/1-0489 project data includes lamb samples from the year 2022, known as the A22 group, and from the year 2023, referred to as the A23, consisting of 76 and 92 intensively fattened lambs from eight breeds. The previously created group will also include samples from 2024, totalling 92 samples.

The database contains genotyping results for 57 SNPs, for which a statistically significant association with one of the feed efficiency indicators was established within the project, using NGS methodology and association statistical methods. The specific SNPs were selected for further work as the first DNA molecular markers for future sheep breeding programmes in Latvia.

In the database, SNPs are coded with a laboratory code and an rs ID number. The gene in which the SNP is located is also indicated. The genotypes of each SNP are presented using standard IUB/IUPAC nucleic acid codes, representing the genotype of two alleles at a single locus with a single letter.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

Genotypic characteristics of intensively fattened lambs are collected in a database so that association analysis can then be performed in relation to any characteristics of sheep.

Within the framework of the existing project, SNP information was used for association analysis with meat quality and quantity indicators.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

- Observation data
- Process produced data
- Other

Molecular analysis data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

XLS

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

100

KB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

Yes

1.1.7 If Yes, please indicate what data set are you re-using?

Animal Genome Size Database

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/>

id: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14224369>, Type: doi

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

The resulting database and its processing results could be useful for molecular biologists for more analysis on other type of breeds in different populations.

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Yes

DOI

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01_Database of meat quality and quantity indicators (carcass characteristics) intensively fattened lambs (Group or feed trial 0) of sheep breeds raised in Latvia, created before the project

The collection of lamb samples was conducted prior to the project. The collection consists of intensively fattened lambs from sheep breeds, including the Latvian Dark-head breed, which were raised in the meadow and are semi-sibi lambs within the scope of the study.

The database contains data on ultrasonography measurements of lambs during the beginning and end of fattening for muscle depth and fat thickness at the 13th rib and intensive fattening data (real and calculated on the 90th and 150th days). The database includes data about meat quality and quantity indicators (carcass characteristics): slaughter weight, carcass length and hip girth, musculature and fat gradient.

Based on the requirements of the breeding programme of the breeds, every year, the offspring of the sire ram, certified for breeding activity, are selected and analysed to estimate the sire rams. All lambs were born as twins, triplets, or quadruplets from different ewes, and health status was assessed prior to inclusion in the study so that there were at least two lambs per sire ram from the breed. This study was carried out in cooperation with the Latvian Sheep Breeders' Association at the ram breeding control station.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The phenotypic indicators of intensively fattened lambs are collected in a database so that association analysis can then be performed in relation to genetic or DNA single nucleotide polymorphism genotyping results.

In previous projects, data was made about fattening, but not meat quality and quantity indicators.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

- Aggregate data
- Observation data
- Process produced data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- TXT
- CSV
- XLS

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

100

KB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

There aren't data on the meat quality and quantity of intensively fattened lambs raised in Latvia in controlled conditions.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

The resulting database and its processing results could be useful for sheep farmers, who could evaluate the results of intensive fattening over time.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

DataverseLV

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

R, Excel, notepad

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

Yes

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

When using data, you must provide a reference to the database, the project from which the data was obtained, or the authors.

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Elina Leonova (0000-0001-6572-4518)

Data management involves entering data obtained during measurements into tables, calculating additional data, describing data sets, evaluating and ensuring data access.

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

Data will be deposited in repository and kept up to date

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Firewall
- Passwords
- Physical access control

The database will be created using security measures that will provide for data access control, as the data will be stored on a data medium that will only be accessible to specific persons. The data medium will have a password set for both

the overall system and the specific database, as well as protections to prevent access from the Internet.

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

02_Database of DNA loci or SNPs, on the SNP chip, genotyping results of DNA samples of intensively fattened lambs (Group or feed trial 0) of sheep breeds raised in Latvia, created before the project.

As a result of the LZP-2021/1-0489 project, 57 DNA loci, or SNPs were discovered that were found to be statistically significantly associated with feed efficiency indicators. The specific loci were genotyped in all LZP-2021/1-0489 project samples and are being used in further research to improve the reliability of the obtained data.

In the database, SNPs are coded with a laboratory code and an rs ID number. The gene in which the SNP is located is also indicated. The genotypes of each SNP are presented using standard IUB/IUPAC nucleic acid codes, representing the genotype of two alleles at a single locus with a single letter.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The significant loci discovered in the previous project are genotyped in DNA samples of intensively fattened lambs from the current project. The obtained

results are compiled in a database so that they can be used in previously developed machine learning algorithms and make improvements/precisions in the prediction process.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

- Aggregate data
- Observation data
- Process produced data
- Other

Molecular analysis data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- TXT
- CSV
- XLS

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

100

KB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

Previously obtained data will be partially used, but it is necessary to increase the data set to be analysed in order to obtain data for a longer period of intensive fattening (currently there is data for 2022 - 2024) and to have higher statistical reliability when analysing the data.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

The resulting database and its processing results could be useful for molecular biologists and/or sheep farmers, more precisely sheep breeders, to (1) compare data with other breeds and (2) create a MAS tool for breed improvement.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

Yes

Comment:

The databases will be fully available after contacting the authors, as the data will contain animal identification numbers and the database will contain information intended for publication and the preparation of know-how.

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

DataverseLV

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

R, Excel, Notepad or Plink

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

Yes

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

When using data, you must provide a reference to the database, the project from which the data was obtained, or the authors.

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2028-11-09

2.4.4 How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

There is no time limit for data reuse, as data is information about a specific time period that can be used in comparative analysis.

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Ilva Trapina (0000-0002-8345-8708)

Data management involves entering data obtained during measurements into tables, calculating additional data, describing data sets, evaluating and ensuring data access.

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

Data will be deposited in repository and kept up to date

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Firewall

- Passwords
- Physical access control

The database will be created using security measures that will provide for data access control, as the data will be stored on a data medium that will only be accessible to specific individuals. The data medium will have a password set for both the overall system and the specific database, as well as protections to prevent access from the Internet.

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

03_Database of identification, fattening indicators and meat quality and quantity indicators (carcass characteristics) of lambs of sheep breeds raised in Latvia and intensively fattened in the 1st year of the project (Feed trial 1; 2025/2026).

Data on lamb samples of the year 2025/2026 (the 1st year of the project; Feed trial 1), which consists of intensively fattened lambs from sheep breeds, including the Latvian Dark-head breed.

The database contains data on ultrasonography measurements of lambs during the beginning and end of fattening for muscle depth and fat thickness at the 13th rib and intensive fattening data (real and calculated on the 90th and 150th days). The database includes data about meat quality and quantity indicators (carcass characteristics): slaughter weight, carcass length and hip girth, musculature and fat gradient.

Based on the requirements of the breeding programme of the breeds, every year, the offspring of the sire ram, certified for breeding activity, are selected and analysed to estimate the sire rams. All lambs were born as twins, triplets, or quadruplets from different ewes, and health status was assessed prior to inclusion in the study so that there were at least two lambs per sire ram from the breed. This study was carried out in cooperation with the Latvian Sheep Breeders' Association at the ram breeding control station.

Template: LCS FARP

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The phenotypic indicators of intensively fattened lambs are collected in a database so that association analysis can then be performed in relation to genetic or DNA single nucleotide polymorphism genotyping results.

By collecting intensive fattening phenotypic data, it is also possible to perform an analysis of lambs fattened in a particular year and compare their data with previous years from the lzp-2021/1-0489 project.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

- Aggregate data
- Observation data
- Process produced data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- TXT
- CSV

- XLS

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

100

KB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

Previously obtained data will be partially used, but it is necessary to increase the data set to be analysed in order to obtain data for a longer period of intensive fattening (currently there is data for 2022 - 2024) and to have higher statistical reliability when analysing the data.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

The resulting database and its processing results could be useful for sheep farmers, who could evaluate the results of intensive fattening over time.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

DataverseLV

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

R, Excel, notepad

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

Yes

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

When using data, you must provide a reference to the database, the project from which the data was obtained, or the authors.

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Elina Leonova (0000-0001-6572-4518)

Data management involves entering data obtained during measurements into tables, calculating additional data, describing data sets, evaluating and ensuring data access.

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

Data will be deposited in repository and kept up to date

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Firewall
- Passwords
- Physical access control

The database will be created using security measures that will provide for data access control, as the data will be stored on a data medium that will only be accessible to specific persons. The data medium will have a password set for both the overall system and the specific database, as well as protections to prevent access from the Internet.

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

04_Database of DNA loci or SNPs, on the SNP chip, genotyping results of lambs of sheep breeds raised in Latvia and intensively fattened in the 1st year of the project (Feed trial 1; 2025/2026).

DNA samples from intensively fattened lambs generated in the 1st year (2025/2026; feed trial 1) will be subjected to a full genome SNP analysis, which includes genotyping of approximately 54k SNPs. The obtained data on locus genotypes will be compiled in a database so that they can be used in association analysis related to feed efficiency and their QTL identification in the Latvian sheep population and individually in the Latvian Dark-head breed.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The collection of WGS data in a database will create the opportunity to use them both in association analysis in a specific project and in future projects and to use them in other studies, for example, comparing them with information available in the public domain - for other breeds.

The existence of the database will also create the opportunity to transfer these data to scientific databases.

By collecting genotypic data from intensive fattening, it is also possible to perform an analysis of lambs fattened in a specific year and compare their data with data from other years and with data from other breeds.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

- Aggregate data
- Observation data
- Process produced data
- Other

Molecular analysis data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- TXT
- CSV
- XLS

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

1

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

It is not possible to use previously created data, as WGS analysis of 54k SNP genotypes has not been performed on samples from the Latvian sheep population. Also, the aim of the study is to analyze samples of intensively matured lambs and samples of sheep raised in Latvia, which are also not available.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

The resulting database and its processing results could be useful for molecular biologists and/or sheep farmers, more precisely sheep breeders, to (1) compare data with other breeds and (2) create a MAS tool for breed improvement.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

Yes

Comment:

The databases will be fully available after contacting the authors, as the data will

contain animal identification numbers and the database will contain information intended for publication and the preparation of know-how.

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

DataverseLV

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

R, Excel, Plink or Notpad

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

Yes

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

When using data, you must provide a reference to the database, the project from which the data was obtained, or the authors.

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2028-08-24

2.4.4 How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

There is no time limit for data reuse, as data is information about a specific time period that can be used in comparative analysis.

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Ilva Trapina (0000-0002-8345-8708)

Data management involves entering data obtained during measurements into tables, calculating additional data, describing data sets, evaluating and ensuring data access.

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

Data will be deposited in repository and kept up to date

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Firewall
- Passwords
- Physical access control

The database will be created using security measures that will provide for data access control, as the data will be stored on a data medium that will only be accessible to specific persons. The data medium will have a password set for both the overall system and the specific database, as well as protections to prevent access from the Internet.

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

05_Database of previously significant 57 SNP genotypes of DNA samples of lambs of sheep breeds raised in Latvia and intensively fattened in the 1st year of the project (Feed trial 1; 2025/2026)

As a result of the LZP-2021/1-0489 project, 57 DNA loci or SNPs were discovered that were found to be statistically significantly associated with feed efficiency indicators. The specific loci were genotyped in all LZP-2021/1-0489 project samples and are being used in further research to improve the reliability of the obtained data.

In the database, SNPs are coded with a laboratory code and an rs ID number. The gene in which the SNP is located is also indicated. The genotypes of each SNP are presented using standard IUB/IUPAC nucleic acid codes, representing the genotype of two alleles at a single locus with a single letter.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The significant loci discovered in the previous project are genotyped in DNA samples of intensively fattened lambs from the current project. The obtained results are compiled in a database so that they can be used in previously developed machine learning algorithms and make improvements/precisions in the prediction process.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

- Aggregate data
- Observation data
- Process produced data
- Other

Molecular analysis data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- TXT
- CSV
- XLS

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

100

KB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

As well as previous years' intensive fattening data being used as the first stage of the study, new data is needed to verify the results obtained in the first stage.

Data from analyses of other breeds/populations cannot be used, as scientific studies have shown that an association in one population/breed may not be repeated in another.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

The resulting database and its processing results could be useful for molecular biologists and/or sheep farmers, more precisely sheep breeders, to (1) compare data with other breeds and (2) create a MAS tool for breed improvement.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

Yes

Comment:

The databases will be fully available after contacting the authors, as the data will

contain animal identification numbers and the database will contain information intended for publication and the preparation of know-how.

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

DataverseLV

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

R, Excel, notepad or Plink

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

Yes

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

When using data, a reference to the database, the project in which the data was obtained, or the authors must be provided.

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2028-11-29

2.4.4 How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

There is no time limit for data reuse, as data is information about a specific time period that can be used in comparative analysis.

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Ilva Trapina (0000-0002-8345-8708)

Data management involves entering data obtained during measurements into tables, calculating additional data, describing data sets, evaluating and ensuring data access

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

Data will be deposited in repository and kept up to date

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Firewall
- Passwords
- Physical access control

The database will be created using security measures that will provide for data access control, as the data will be stored on a data medium that will only be accessible to specific persons. The data medium will have a password set for both the overall system and the specific database, as well as protections to prevent access from the Internet.

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

06_ Database of association analysis of DNA loci genotyped on the SNP chip and the previously significant 57 SNPs with meat quality and quantity indicators (carcass characteristics) results.

Genome-wide sequencing methodologies (GWAS, genome-wide association studies) are used to determine specific QTL traits related to productive characteristics in the sheep genome. Researchers can use genetic variations found in specific QTL regions associated with sheep productive traits as molecular markers for MAS (marker-assisted selection) in sheep breeding.

MAS relies on established relationships between DNA regions and specific quantitative trait loci (QTL) within a breed. Marker-assisted selection provides an excellent instrument for identifying desirable traits. First, it can help choose crossbred offspring with the right genetic profiles and estimated breeding values (EBVs) for traits related to carcass quality, which will improve the results of crossbreeding. Second, analysing the genetic markers of already born lambs enables the prediction of their productive potential, aiding decisions about their inclusion in breeding programs.

Analyse the association between the value of the above phenotypic and meat quality and quantity indicators and genetic variations. Develop a panel of molecular markers associated with the meat quality and quantity indicator parameters.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

By performing a statistical or association analysis between meat quality and quantity indicator parameters and the SNPs genotyped as a result of GWAS, data will be obtained for each of the meat quality and quantity indicators. The results will include both information about a possible QTL region in the sheep genome and a statistically reliable association between a specific SNP and the meat quality and quantity indicator.

The database will collect SNPs or DNA loci for which an association has been established with a statistical reliability of $P < 0.05$ and/or $P < 1 \times 10^{-6}$.

The information contained in the database will be used for further studies: (1) to develop a manual genotyping method; (2) to validate the obtained association in DNA samples of intensively fattened lambs in 2020; (3) to develop know-how and provide recommendations for sheep farmers.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

- Aggregate data
- Process produced data
- Other

Association analyze data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- TXT
- CSV
- XLS

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

1

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

It is not possible to use previously created data, as WGS analysis of 54k SNP genotypes has not been performed on samples from the Latvian sheep population.

Data from other breeds/populations cannot be used, as studies show that associations in one breed/population may not be repeated in another.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

The resulting database and its processing results could be useful for molecular biologists and/or sheep farmers, more precisely sheep breeders, to (1) compare data with other breeds and (2) create a MAS tool for breed improvement.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

Yes

Comment:

The databases will be fully available after contacting the authors, as the data will contain animal identification numbers and the database will contain information intended for publication and the preparation of know-how.

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

DataverseLV

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

R, Excel, notpad

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

Yes

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

No

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

Yes

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

When using data, a reference to the database, the project in which the data was obtained, or the authors must be provided.

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2028-11-16

2.4.4 How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

There is no time limit for data reuse, as data is information about a specific time period that can be used in comparative analysis.

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Ilva Trapina (0000-0002-8345-8708)

Data management involves entering data obtained during measurements into tables, calculating additional data, describing data sets, evaluating and ensuring data access.

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

Data will be deposited in repository and kept up to date

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Firewall
- Passwords
- Physical access control

The database will be created using security measures that will provide for data access control, as the data will be stored on a data medium that will only be accessible to specific persons. The data medium will have a password set for both the overall system and the specific database, as well as protections to prevent access from the Internet.

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

07_Database of SNP associated with meat quality and quantity indicators in DNA samples of lambs of sheep breeds raised in Latvia and intensively fattened before the project and in the 1st year of the project (Feed trial 0 and 1).

The GWAS will result in a database containing information on more than 54K DNA loci, of which only a small fraction could be QTL or related to meat quality and quantity indicators. By performing a statistical or association analysis between meat quality and quantity indicator parameters and the SNPs genotyped as a result of GWAS, data will be obtained for each of the meat quality and quantity indicators. The significant loci will be identified in the association analysis and copied to the database.

Accordingly, it will be necessary to create a database containing information only on specific SNPs in all intensively fattened lambs analysed so that, using this specific database, machine learning algorithms can be developed for the determination of estimated breeding values (EBVs) or the use of MAS.

The database will collect SNPs or DNA loci for which an association has been established with a statistical significance of $P < 0.05$ and/or $P < 1 \times 10^{-6}$.

The information contained in the database will be used for further studies: (1) to develop a manual genotyping method; (2) to validate the obtained association in DNA samples of intensively fattened lambs in 2026; (3) to develop know-how and provide recommendations for sheep farmers.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

Accordingly, it will be necessary to create a database containing information only on specific SNPs in all intensively fattened lambs analyzed, so that using this specific database, machine learning algorithms can be developed for the determination of estimated breeding values (EBVs) or the use of MAS.

The information contained in the database will be used for further studies: (1) to develop a manual genotyping method; (2) to validate the obtained association in DNA samples of intensively fattened lambs in 2020; (3) to develop know-how and provide recommendations for sheep farmers.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

- Aggregate data
- Experimental data
- Observation data
- Process produced data
- Other

Association analyze data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- TXT
- CSV
- XLS

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

1

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

It is not possible to use previously created data, as WGS analysis of 54k SNP genotypes has not been performed on samples from the Latvian sheep population.

It is also not possible to use data from analyses of other breeds/populations, as scientific studies have shown that an association in one population/breed may not be repeated in another.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

The resulting database and its processing results could be useful for molecular biologists and/or sheep farmers, more precisely sheep breeders, to (1) compare data with other breeds and (2) create a MAS tool for breed improvement.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

Yes

Comment:

The databases will be fully available after contacting the authors, as the data will contain animal identification numbers and the database will contain information intended for publication and the preparation of know-how.

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

DataverseLV

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

R, Excel, notepad

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

Yes

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

When using data, a reference to the database, the project in which the data was obtained, or the authors must be provided.

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2028-12-29

2.4.4 How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

There is no time limit for data reuse, as data is information about a specific time period that can be used in comparative analysis.

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Ilva Trapina (0000-0002-8345-8708)

Data management involves entering data obtained during measurements into tables, calculating additional data, describing data sets, evaluating and ensuring data access.

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

Data will be deposited in repository and kept up to date

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Firewall
- Passwords
- Physical access control

The database will be created using security measures that will provide for data access control, as the data will be stored on a data medium that will only be accessible to specific persons. The data medium will have a password set for both the overall system and the specific database, as well as protections to prevent access from the Internet.

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

08_Database of identification, fattening indicators, and meat quality and quantity indicators (carcass characteristics) of lambs of sheep breeds raised in Latvia and intensively fattened in the 2nd year of the project (Feed trial 2; 2027).

Data on lamb samples of the year 2027 (the 2st year of the project; Feed trial 2), which consists of intensively fattened lambs from sheep breeds, including the Latvian Dark-head breed.

The database contains data on ultrasonography measurements of lambs during the beginning and end of fattening for muscle depth and fat thickness at the 13th rib and intensive fattening data (real and calculated on the 90th and 150th days). The database includes data about meat quality and quantity indicators (carcass characteristics): slaughter weight, carcass length and hip girth, musculature and fat gradient.

Based on the requirements of the breeding programme of the breeds, every year, the offspring of the sire ram, certified for breeding activity, are selected and analysed to estimate the sire rams. All lambs were born as twins, triplets, or quadruplets from different ewes, and health status was assessed prior to inclusion in the study so that there were at least two lambs per sire ram from the breed. This study was carried out in cooperation with the Latvian Sheep Breeders' Association at the ram breeding control station.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The phenotypic indicators of intensively fattened lambs are collected in a database so that association analysis can then be performed in relation to genetic or DNA single nucleotide polymorphism genotyping results.

By collecting intensive fattening phenotypic data, it is also possible to perform an analysis of lambs fattened in a particular year and compare their data with previous years.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

- Aggregate data
- Observation data
- Process produced data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- TXT
- CSV
- XLS

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

100

KB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

Previously obtained data will be partially used; however, it is necessary to expand the data set being analysed to include a longer period of intensive fattening, which will enhance the statistical reliability of the analysis.

It was the first stage of the study, but new data is needed to verify the results.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

The resulting database and its processing results could be useful for sheep farmers, who could evaluate the results of intensive fattening over time.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

DataverseLV

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

R, Excel, notepad

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

Yes

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

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When using data, a reference to the database, the project in which the data was obtained, or the authors must be provided.

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.4 How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

There is no time limit for data reuse, as data is information about a specific time period that can be used in comparative analysis.

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Elina Leonova (0000-0001-6572-4518)

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

Data will be deposited in repository and kept up to date

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Firewall
- Passwords
- Physical access control

The database will be created using security measures that will provide for data access control, as the data will be stored on a data medium that will only be accessible to specific persons. The data medium will have a password set for both the overall system and the specific database, as well as protections to prevent access from the Internet.

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

09_Database of SNP, associated with meat quality and quantity indicators, genotyping results of DNA samples of lambs of sheep breeds raised in Latvia and intensively fattened in the 2nd year of the project (Feed trial 2; 2027).

The GWAS will result in a database containing information on more than 54K DNA loci, of which only a small fraction could be QTL or related to meat quality and quantity indicators. By performing a statistical or association analysis between meat quality and quantity indicators and the SNPs genotyped as a result of GWAS, data will be obtained for each of the meat quality and quantity indicators. The significant loci will be identified in the association analysis and will be copied into the database.

The database will collect SNPs or DNA loci for which an association has been established with a statistical significance of $P < 0.05$ and/or $P < 1 \times 10^{-6}$.

The selected SNPs or DNA loci will be genotyped in DNA samples from intensively fattened lambs from the second year of the project, thus creating a database that will compile the genotyping results of each lamb sample.

A database with information only on specific SNPs will be used to validate (1) the statistical association of loci found in the first phase of the project and (2) the use of common molecular marker panels using these to determine estimated breeding values (EBV) or use them in MAS.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The selected SNPs or DNA loci will be genotyped in DNA samples from intensively fattened lambs from the second year of the project, thus creating a database that will compile the genotyping results of each lamb sample.

A database containing information solely on specific SNPs will be used to validate (1) the statistical association of loci identified in the first phase of the project and (2) the application of common molecular marker panels to determine estimated breeding values (EBV) or to use them in marker-assisted selection (MAS).

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

- Aggregate data
- Experimental data
- Observation data
- Process produced data
- Other

Molecular analysis data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- TXT
- CSV
- XLS

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

100

KB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

It is not possible to use previously created data, as previous years' intensive fattening data was used as the first stage of the study, but new data is needed to verify the results obtained in the first stage.

Data from analyses of other breeds/populations cannot be used because scientific studies have shown that an association in one population/breed may not be repeated in another.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

The resulting database and its processing results could be useful for molecular biologists and/or sheep farmers, more precisely sheep breeders, to (1) compare data with other breeds and (2) create a MAS tool for breed improvement.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

Yes

Comment:

The databases will be fully available after contacting the authors, as the data will contain animal identification numbers and the database will contain information intended for publication and the preparation of know-how.

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

DataverseLV

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

R, Excel, notepad or Plink

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

Yes

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

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When using data, you must provide a reference to the database, the project from which the data was obtained, or the authors.

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.4 How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

There is no time limit for data reuse, as data is information about a specific time period that can be used in comparative analysis.

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Ilva Trapina (0000-0002-8345-8708)

Data management involves entering data obtained during measurements into tables, calculating additional data, describing data sets, evaluating and ensuring data access.

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

Data will be deposited in repository and kept up to date

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Firewall
- Passwords
- Physical access control

The database will be created using security measures that will provide for data access control, as the data will be stored on a data medium that will only be accessible to specific persons. The data medium will have a password set for both the overall system and the specific database, as well as protections to prevent access from the Internet.

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

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